

Physical Properties of Fatty Acid Esters of 1,2-Propane Diol. Part-I : 1-Monoesters and Monoacid Diesters

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Pure monoacid diesters and 1-monoesters of 1,2-propane diol of odd chain fatty acids as well as of two higher even chain fatty acids were prepared and their physical properties determined. The odd and even chain fatty acid esters behave as two separate series, with respect to their melting behaviour : when considered as one series, alternation in the m.p. is evident. The changes in density and refractive index due to graded increases in molecular weight of the diesters, differ slightly for short and long chain fatty acid esters ; dipropionate has the lowest viscosity amongst the diesters.

PHYSCAL properties of 1-monoesters, monoacid diesters, and diacid diesters of 1,2-propane diol (pg) of even chain fatty acids were reported earlier¹⁻³. In this paper, data on the properties of pg esters (1-monoesters and monoacid diesters) of odd chain acids as well as of arachidic and behenic acids are being reported. The properties of diacid diesters from odd chain fatty acids are also communicated in part II*.

Experimental

Fatty acids used in the synthesis were obtained as follows. Pure short chain fatty acids from propionic to nonanoic were obtained by fractional distillation of the acids or methyl esters of their respective commercial stocks. The odd chain fatty acids from tri- to nonadecanoic were prepared from the appropriate glc pure even chain fatty alcohols through the nitrile route as described recently⁴. Arachidic and behenic acids were prepared from kumud and mustard oils, respectively, by fractional distillation of their fatty acid-methyl esters, hydrogenating the relevant fractions and solvent crystallization. Undecanoic acid was similarly prepared from methyl undecylenate originating from pyrolysis of castor oil.

The methods followed for preparation, purification and determination of the physical properties of the 1-monoesters and monoacid diesters are similar to those described earlier¹⁻³. 1-Monoesters of pg were prepared by reacting glc pure fatty acids with large excess of pg (15 moles per mole) in chloroform using *para*-toluene sulphonic acid as catalyst for 4-5 hr, continuously removing the water of reaction azeotropically. Under the conditions, the product was predominantly 1-monoesters with small amounts of 2-monoesters and diesters. The catalyst was inactivated, solvent was removed and the crude monoesters were purified by repeated crystallization

from hexane to a constant m.p. TLC showed the absence of fatty acids, 2-monoesters and diesters.

Monoacid diesters were prepared by acylation of the pure 1-monoesters taken in chloroform in the presence of pyridine at 15°. Appropriate acid chloride (1.2 mole per mole) was added slowly to the reactants while stirring and maintaining the temperature. After addition, the temperature was allowed to rise to room temperature and left at that till acylation is complete, as monitored by tlc. The contents were washed and freed from chloroform. The dipropionate was purified by fractional distillation, whilst the others were purified by solvent crystallization and/or column chromatography over suitable adsorbents.

Results and Discussion

The relationships between m.p. (of the highest melting form obtained by tempering), density, refractive index, viscosity and the number of carbon atoms in the acyl chains of the esters are shown in Figs. 1-4, respectively.

The m.p.s of 1-monoesters of arachidic and behenic acids agree closely with earlier reported values⁵ (Table 1), and the other are being reported for the first time. Alternation in the melting behaviour (Fig. 1) is evident when the odd and even chain fatty acid esters are considered as one series. This phenomenon of alternation, seen here for the pg esters and reported to occur for fatty acids and some of their derivatives, is due to significant geometric differences between the crystal structures of the odd and even chain acids during solidification. The influence of number of carbon atoms in acyl chain is further accentuated by the presence of methyl group in 1,2-propane diol.

* J. Indian Chem. Soc., 1983, 60, 1065.

Fig. 1. Relationship of the m.p. and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid of (A) 1-monoesters and (B) monoacid diesters of pg (solid points are reported values¹).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF 1-MONOESTERS AND MONOACID DIESTERS OF 1,2-PROPANE DIOL

Ester	m.p. (β -Form) °C	Density at 80° g/ml	Refractive index n_D^{80}	Viscosity at 80° cps
1-Monoesters				
Heptadecanoate	38.6	0.8582	1.4288	4.99
Nonadecanoate	48.0	0.8545	1.4310	5.98
Arachidate	54.5(54.5 ^a)	0.8538	1.4317	6.33
Behenate	62.2(62.1 ^a)	0.8514	1.4322	7.49
Monoacid diesters				
Propionate	—	0.9542	1.3920	0.90
Valerate	—	0.9080	1.4015	1.22
Heptanoate	—	0.8857	1.4098	1.62
Nonanoate	—	0.8727	1.4170	2.24
Undecanoate	—	0.8656	1.4224	2.99
Tridecanoate	22.3	0.8581	1.4265	3.76
Pentadecanoate	36.2	0.8580	1.4292	4.91
Heptadecanoate	48.3	0.8497	1.4318	6.22
Nonadecanoate	56.5	0.8471	1.4340	7.70
Arachidate	62.7	0.8464	1.4348	8.64
Behenate	69.4	0.8464	1.4357	9.87

Fig. 2. Relationship of density and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid of monoacid diesters of pg at different temperatures (solid points are reported values^{1,2}).

The m.p. of 1-monoarachidate falls slightly below the m.p. curve of the other even chain esters, and this could be attributed to its inability to crystallize

out in a stable form analogous with other pg esters, as claimed earlier⁵. The monoesters melt lower than their corresponding diesters which in turn melt at a temperature lower than the parent fatty acids, unlike for the glycerol esters where monoacid triglycerides have m.p. lower, than those of their corresponding monoglycerides. This also may be due to the influence of the methyl group on the closeness of molecular packing in the solid state.

Fig. 3. Relationship of refractive index and number of carbon atoms in the fatty acid of monoacid diesters of pg at different temperatures (solid points are reported values^{1,2}).

In the liquid state, the 1-monoesters have higher densities, but lower refractive indices and viscosities than their corresponding monoacid diesters, at all the temperatures studied (data at only one temperature is given in Table 1). Whilst ascending a homologous series, the density decreases, refractive index and viscosity increases progressively and these changes are not linear with the regular increases in the length of the acyl chain present (Figs. 2-4). The changes in density and refractive index, as the series is ascended in a graded manner, is more for the short chain esters than for the long chain ones. The reverse is true for viscosity within the temperature range studied (40-80°).

There exists a linear relationship between density or refractive index and temperature for each of the studied compounds, whilst log viscosity is proportional to the reciprocal of the absolute temperature. From the plots (not reproduced here), the calculated temperature coefficients for density and refractive index for monoacid diesters from undecanoate and higher are -7.01×10^{-4} and -3.99×10^{-4} , respectively. These values compare well with those reported earlier³ for even chain fatty acid esters (-6.98×10^{-4} and -3.97×10^{-4}). For the lower monoacid diesters, the temperature coefficients progressively increase with decrease in their molecular weight.

Amongst the monoacid diesters, dipropionate has the lowest viscosity (Fig. 4). The viscosity of pg dipropionate at 40° is 1.52 cps and the reported³ viscosities of pg diacetate and dibutyrate at the same

Fig. 4. Relationship of viscosity and number of carbon atoms in fatty acids of pg diesters at different temperatures.

temperature are 1.85 and 1.77 cps, respectively. The higher viscosity of pg diacetate over propionate

could be due to the predominant influence of the polar attraction forces between the molecules in the former which are perceptibly weakened by the acyl chain of the latter. With subsequent increase in the length of acyl chain beyond dipropionate, the viscosity increases due to the progressive dominance of the non polar forces.

References

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